

FORECASTING OF LONG-TERM ELECTRICAL LOAD DEMAND USING RECURRENT NEURAL NETWORK

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Abstract

Electrical load demand forecasting is an essential process in power system planning and operation, enabling utilities to optimize resource allocation, ensuring grid stability and facilitating demand-side management (DSM). This study employs a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) to estimate the electricity demand in Ado-Ekiti Metropolis, Nigeria, for the period 2021 to 2030. The model was developed and simulated using MATLAB 9.0.0 (R2016b) curve fitting tools to establish the effectiveness of RNN in load forecasting. The RNN model was implemented as a nonlinear system utilizing a backpropagation learning algorithm to capture complex temporal dependencies in electricity consumption. The results indicate that the average annual predicted energy consumption over ten-year period is 1127 MW. Findings reveal a consistent increase in energy demand at the 11kV injection substation, particularly for Adebayo and Agric feeders, highlighting the necessity for proactive energy planning. The study emphasizes that accurate load forecasting helps electricity providers optimize power distribution, reduces operational losses and supports pricing mechanisms for potential investors. Integrating demand forecasting with generation planning is essential for maintaining a reliable power supply in Nigeria's evolving electricity market. By leveraging deep learning techniques like RNN, utilities can enhance their forecasting capabilities, improve grid efficiency and ensure sustainable energy management.

Keywords

*Energy Consumption,
Injection Substation,
Load Forecasting,
MATLAB,
RNN*

1. INTRODUCTION

Electricity demand forecasting plays a central role in the process of power system planning and operation. Electrical energy cannot be stored, but must be generated whenever there is a demand for it. It is imperative for the electric power utilities that the load on their systems should be estimated in advance. This estimation of load in advance is commonly known as load forecasting. Load forecasting measures the exactness of the difference between the actual and predicted value of future load demand. [1] posited that forecasting capability brings helpful insights for security of energy supply, supporting power companies in providing their end-users with advanced demand-side services and safe and stable systems.

Nigeria is faced with the challenges of inadequate electricity supply because power demand is on the increase daily just as there is a shift from power generation to more sophisticated power stations. In a bid to tackle the inadequacy of electricity, deregulation of electricity was employed as an alternative. Several planning operational tasks such as a great deal of statistical analysis, modelling and forecasting ranging from generation to pricing is required for effectiveness [2]. Owing to expansion, socio-economic development, industrialization, proliferation of buildings, rural-urban migration witnessed in urban areas like Ado-Ekiti Metropolis, demands for electricity grows. The surplus power capacity (in megawatts) generated from the source, transmitted and distributed are no longer sufficient for the dwellers and its attendant challenges [3].

Several studies have been conducted on forecasting electrical energy demands. [2] investigated recurrent neural network model for forecasting electrical energy demands in Nigeria. The study used climatic, demographic and economic factors as significant inputs in developing neural network architecture to forecast electricity demand in

Nigeria and the predicted load for 2015 is about 550GWh with an expected demand increase of 7.5 % every five years.

[4] compared the predictive capabilities of feed-forward neural networks (FFNN) and long short-term memory networks (LSTM) in electricity load forecasting in which LSTM outperforms FFNN in electricity load forecasting due to its ability to learn and remember time-based patterns, making it more accurate and reliable for time-series prediction. [5] gave an overview as well as the techniques for the Short term load forecasting using the weather parameter like rainfall and implementing a neural network technique in the power systems. Rainfall in short-term load forecasting (STLF) enhances prediction accuracy, particularly in regions affecting electricity usage. LSTM models with rainfall data achieve 5-15% better accuracy, especially in tropical or rain-sensitive regions. Hybrid neural networks enhance performance.

[6] considered ANN approach and local utility station of Ogbomoso Distribution Station, Nigeria was the focal point. The result obtained from this research shows the efficiency of artificial neural network and the accuracy of short-term method of load forecasting. Power system expansion planning starts with a forecast of anticipated future load requirements. There is a growing tendency towards unbundling the electricity system. This is continually confronting the different sectors of the industry (generation, transmission and distribution) with increasing demand for planning management and operations of the network. The operation and planning of a power utility company require an adequate model for electric power load forecasting. Load forecasting plays a key role in helping an electric utility to make important decisions on power, load switching, voltage control, network reconfiguration, and infrastructure development [7]. Economic implications of power utility such as scheduling of generating capacity, fuel purchases, security analysis, planning of power development maintenance scheduling, and dispatching of generation units are operated based on accurate load forecasting.

Load forecasting is challenging due to variability in load time series, system load consisting of thousands of independent components, and the influence of variables like weather, social events, economic factors, and demographic features on consumption patterns [8]. There are different methods of forecasting or load predictions including statistical approaches (multiple regression, stochastic time series, iterative reweighted least square), and artificial intelligence approaches (Artificial Neural Network (ANN)) etc.

An RNN is a type of ANN with one or more feedback loops from the output or from other layers in the network. RNNs are potentially more powerful for forecasting than the Feed Forward Neural Network (FFNN) because of the ability of RNN to recognize and recall spatio-temporal patterns [2]. The need to understand the power demand a town as it grows and develops necessitated the application of recurrent neural network (RNN) to plan ahead in terms of service delivery, maintenance and expansion of power facilities. "One network type is the recurrent neural network (RNN), designed to work with sequential data. The strength of an RNN is that it can take information from prior inputs together with the input at a given timestamp to better decide on the output" [9]. The output of an RNN is a function of time [2]. In a developing economy, an RNN is appropriate for forecasting electricity demand because the electricity demand data are incomplete and noisy due to shortage in supply. Future may not necessarily follow the past because developing economies are undergoing economic transition and increasing diffusion of technologies in the society. In addition, electricity consumption is largely influenced by human needs and societal objectives which are not well defined ahead and can change with human and global development [10].

The findings from the reviewed literature showed that while various studies have been conducted on electricity load forecasting in Nigeria, none have specifically focused on the Ado-Ekiti metropolis, particularly for the period of 2021-2030. Furthermore, previous research has not extensively utilized Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) models for this specific geographical area, nor have they provided a detailed analysis of the load demand on the Adebayo and Agric feeders within Ado-Ekiti. This study aims to fill these gaps by providing a long-term load forecast for Ado-Ekiti and demonstrating the effectiveness of the RNN model in this context. The objective of this paper is to develop an optimum computational architecture in modular Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) model to forecast electricity demand. Thus, the ultimate focus is to build a model for predicting electricity demand and hence aid investors and government in making appropriate investment decisions and serve as input towards achieving certain socio-economic objectives.

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

2.1. RNN Model Description

Figure 1 shows the model architecture adopted from Electric Load Forecasting in Smart Grids Using Long Short-Term Memory-Based Recurrent Neural Network.

Given an input time series $\mathbf{x} = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_T\}$, the RNN computes the hidden state sequence $\mathbf{h} = \{h_1, h_2, \dots, h_T\}$ and the output sequence $\mathbf{y} = \{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_T\}$ iteratively using the following equations:

$$h_t = f(W_{hx}x_t + W_{hh}h_{t-1} + b_h) \quad (1)$$

$$y_t = g(W_{yh}h_t + b_y) \quad (2)$$

where W_{hx} , W_{hh} , and W_{yh} are the input–hidden, hidden–hidden, and hidden–output weight matrices, respectively; b_h and b_y representing the bias of the hidden layer and the output layers; $f(h_t)$ and $g(y_t)$ are the activation functions for the hidden and the output layers, respectively. The RNN uses the hidden state h_t at time step t to retain information from previous states [11].

Fig. 1. RNN Architecture

2.2. Data Preparation and Training Procedure

The time series data, spanning from 2016 to 2020 (a total of 5 years), was obtained from six injection substations. The data was divided into three sets in the ratio of 14:3:3 for training, testing, and validation, respectively.

The outlier removal discards values outside the range of 95% of a normally distributed data set that lies within two standard deviations of the mean aiming at producing a network with a smoother learning curve. Problems of quantity check were overcome by enlarging the data set and reducing its dimensionality also for missing data or data not captured the average of the previous three years for the particular month and three years forward where applicable is substituted as the case may be. Even distribution of training samples was ensured to build a well-balanced model through quantity checks. Data Normalization, as a method of variable scaling, is used to convert input variables with different natural scales (different units of measurement) to a common scale such that the rescaled input span similar ranges of values, though such rescaling is done independently for each variable. The data for the study is transformed into an index in the range of 0 to 1. The data for training the network is a set of four variables containing month count M , number of load points N , year representation Yr , number of transformers connected N_T , and estimated electricity load demand Ld value. The data is divided into three in the ratio of 14:3:3 for training, testing, and validating respectively. Each dataset, comprising sequential concurrent data, is presented to the network as a cell array. The output is also structured as sequential data, ensuring that training is carried out on a set at each instance. Dummy variables R are introduced to meet MATLAB's specific requirement for ten variable values per dataset at each time step, ensuring compatibility with the software's input structure. As presented in Equations (3) and (4).

$$Input = \{[M], [N], [Yr], [NT], [R], [R], [R], [R], [R], [R]\} \quad (3)$$

$$Output = \{[Ld], [R], [R], [R], [R], [R], [R], [R], [R], [R]\} \quad (4)$$

The necessity to open up the possibility of highly accurate predictions was tested through testing for non-linearity and transform into non-linear form. Testing nonlinearity in time series data was carried out by the method of surrogate data which is a statistical approach that involves computing the discriminating statistics for the original time series and the surrogate data sets. The preliminary test for data non-linearity was done after the training data was normalized to fall within 0 and 1 using curve fitting tools, MATLAB 9.0.0 (R2016b), to establish the appropriateness of RNN for forecasting the electrical load. The curve fitting tool provides applications and functions for fitting curves and surfaces to data. It is mainly useful for exploratory data analysis, data preprocessing, and post-processing, to compare models and remove outliers.

The curve fitting procedure in MATLAB is done by loading data at the MATLAB command line, and then opening the curve fitting toolbox and selecting the curve fitting tool. The X and Y data were selected, and the different fit options were tried. The smoothing spline was used to fit the number of loads data owing to a non-parametric fit type. The smoothing spline was applied to fit the load predicted.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the pre-training test for non-linearity and transformation to non-linearity, where applicable, using the curve fitting toolbox in MATLAB are shown in Figures 2 and 3. The number of load points data were fitted with the non-parametric model whose objective is to draw a curve through the data using the smoothing spline.

Fig. 2. Fit for number of load points

Fit analysis of Fig.1: Smoothing spline: $f(x) =$ piecewise polynomial computed from p
Smoothing parameter: $p = 0.9$; SSE: 4.65; R-square: 0.9173; Adjusted R-square: 0.7794; RMSE: 1.062.

Fig. 3. Fit for load demand predicted

The adjusted R-square values, such as 0.7794 for Figure 2 and 0.537 for Figure 3, indicate that while the model captures a significant portion of the variance, there is still room for improvement. These values suggest that other factors not included in the model may influence the load points and predicted load, representing a limitation of the current model. Future research could explore incorporating additional variables to enhance predictive accuracy.

Figures 4 – 7 show the results obtained after the training procedure. Figure 4 shows that the best performance of 0.91473 was obtained at an epoch of 1000 (1000 iterations), Figure 5 shows the performance interface for recurrent neural network, it shows the neurons, inputs layer, hidden layer and the output layer, other parameters such as epoch, time, performance, and gradient are also displayed on the interface. Fig. 6 shows the variation of the

gradient during the training. Fig. 7 depicts that the Target Energy and the predicted energy demand are very close, this confirms low error resulting in the invalidity of the RNN training.

Fig. 4. Performance plot

Fig. 5. The performance plot is shown on the interface

Fig. 6. Gradient obtained during training

Fig. 7. Comparison of the predicted and Target Energy

3.1. Load demand forecasting (LDF) on the 11kv injection substation

The load demand forecasting on the 11kV injection substation reveals a consistent increase in energy consumption across several feeders over the ten-year forecast period (2021-2030), as depicted in Figures 8 to 17. The results for year 2021 indicate a high initial energy prediction, with the Adebayo feeder showing a significantly higher energy demand compared to the Agric, Ureje, Okesha, Basiri, and Ajilosun feeders. However, a decline in energy consumption was observed across the feeders as the year progressed. In year 2022 to 2027, the predicted energy trend for this period suggests that the Agric feeder will experience the highest average energy prediction. Conversely, the Ureje feeder is likely to have the lowest energy prediction. The Basiri feeder is also expected to have a high energy prediction, although it may experience a rapid drop in energy demand for a few months. Also, in year 2028-2030 for the final years of the forecast, the Ureje feeder is predicted to have the highest energy forecast in comparison to the other feeders.

3.2. Feedback propagation architecture forecast for a ten-year load demand

The feedback propagation architecture can be used to forecast ten-year load demand because a feed forward artificial neural network which is a simple deep neural network consists of more than the typical three layers of

multiple layer perceptron. The deep structure increases the feature abstraction capability of neural networks. The number of layers and neurons are the key to modelling neural network structures. The network, having a single hidden layer can vary the number of neurons in a single hidden layer while the depth of the network can be varied in DNN. The number of hidden layers is selected based on forecasting accuracy. This finding is supported by [12] who noted that the conventional methodology of load forecast is incapable of forecasting high accuracy, besides; it is restricted to electricity load data with monthly or a year. They proposed Recurrent Neural Network consisting of Long-Short-Term-Memory (LSTM-RNN) cells as a new method for load forecasting. Having implemented the proposed model on real time data of ISO New England Electricity Market, Recurrent Neural Network proved to be highly accurate for electricity demand predictions and favourable for offline training to forecast electricity load for a period of five years.

The present findings are supported by [13] who revealed that despite the relative simplicity of all reviewed models, the regression analysis is still widely used and efficient for long-term forecasting. As for short-term predictions, machine learning or artificial intelligence-based models such as Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Support Vector Machines (SVM) and Fuzzy logic are favored. In contrast to the findings of the study, the findings of [14] showed that generalized additive models and deep neural networks are other artificial intelligence capable of predicting high-resolution electricity peak demand. Also, [15] evaluated electrical load demand using diverse machine learning algorithms. The study indicated that long short-term memory, which is one of the machine learning algorithms, has the capacity to power load. In addition, [16] affirmed that Long Short-Term Memory is more accurate and can be applied for real time load demand forecasting than Artificial Neural Network (ANN) model.

Fig. 8. Predicted energy for the year 2021

Fig. 9. Predicted energy for the year 2022

Fig. 10. Predicted energy for the year 2023

Fig. 11. Predicted energy for the year 2024

Fig. 12. Predicted energy for the year 2025

Fig. 13. Predicted energy for the year 2026

Fig. 14. Predicted energy for the year 2027

Fig.15. Predicted energy for the year 2028

Fig.16. Predicted energy for the year 2029

Fig.17. Predicted energy for the year 2030

4. CONCLUSION

The study used a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) model to forecast electrical energy demand in Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria. The model, trained using historical data, showed an upward trend in energy demand, with an average annual energy prediction consumption of 1127 MW for ten years. This suggests the need for infrastructure expansion, demand-side management strategies, and proactive power distribution planning. The study emphasizes the importance of integrating AI techniques in power system planning for a more resilient and sustainable energy supply. While this study provides a robust forecasting model, it is important to suggest avenues for future research. The current model primarily relies on historical load data. Future work could explore integrating additional exogenous variables such as weather data (temperature, humidity), economic indicators (GDP, population growth), and social events (holidays, major events) to further enhance predictive accuracy and provide a more comprehensive understanding of demand fluctuations. Additionally, exploring other advanced deep learning architectures, such as Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks or Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs), could potentially yield even more accurate forecasts. Further research could also focus on developing a real-time forecasting system and investigating the impact of demand-side management strategies on load profiles.

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